

COMPARATIVE MULTI-METHOD NDE OF POLYMER MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Polymer materials differ from metals in many physical properties. Methods of nondestructive evaluation (NDE) which are successfully applicable to metals may not be so meaningful for polymers, and vice versa. To give an example, many polymer materials can be inspected with electromagnetic waves. The consequence is that some new methods of NDE appear for polymers, and each one responds to a certain physical aspect of faults. We show how various methods compare if they are applied to certain features.

INTRODUCTION

Polymer materials differ from metals, e. g. by the kind of elements involved, by microstructure, density, electrical and thermal conductivity etc. The consequence is that the NDE methods which are applicable differ for both kinds of materials. There is also a strong difference in the way how the materials can fail under various conditions. Especially fibre reinforced polymers may have all kinds of defects which need to be distinguished from each other if one wants to characterise failure. So one is faced with the problem how a variety of methods can be used to characterise a broad spectrum of potential defects and failure.

A certain detection method may respond to several kinds of defects, and one kind of defect may be inspected with various methods. This situation could be described by a matrix relating methods to defects. Then one has to decide how well a certain defect can be found with various methods. At this stage the question arises whether the application of two or more methods may

provide better information than just one. An example of this correlating NDE is presented in Fig. 1. The objects under inspection were metal/rubber joints some of which were known to contain flaws. It was found that no method was suited to distinguish the two groups from each other, but when for each sample the data obtained from dielectric spectroscopy were plotted versus the frequency of first mechanical resonance frequency, two clusters were formed (“good“ and “no good“) whose projections into each axis strongly overlapped. So the correlation provided more information [1]. This example is well suited to demonstrate the principle of comparative or correlating NDE. The general situation may be more complicated especially if imaging is involved.

Figure 1. Distinction of good/no good samples by correlation of data from vibration analysis and dielectric spectroscopy [1]

IMAGING OF DEFECTS

The detection of defects depends on the kind of interaction between the wave that is used for probing and the physical nature of the defect. Therefore, depending on the NDE method, the defect under inspection may appear different: Each method shows the defect in the light of a specific physical property.

In some cases the defect may look very similar in various methods. An example is impact damage in CFRP where four different methods were applied: Conventional ultrasonic C-scan, lockin-thermography with ultrasonic excitation [2] at 40 KHz with amplitude modulation at 0.03 Hz, lockin-thermography with warm air jet modulated at 0.47 Hz [3], and speckle-interferometry (ESPI). The information is about the same, though the contrast mechanism is reflection or loss angle of mechanical waves, reflection of modulated heat transport, or influence of subsurface structure on surface deformation when thermal expansion is involved. The reason for this

similarity is that the delamination correlated with an impact is a strong impedance mismatch for any kind of excitation. In this case the decision on the method depends on the convenience of the method. Ultrasonics require physical contact (water) with the sample, interferometry is difficult in a rough environment, while lockin-thermography is a remote method requiring modified thermographic equipment to eliminate artefacts [4-6].

Figure 2. Air bubble generated with gas injection moulding inspected with ultrasonic C-scan (a), lockin-thermography (b), and microwave raster scan (c) [7].

Fig. 2 presents NDE results on structure generated with gas injection moulding technique (GIT). We compare ultrasonic C-scan (a), lockin-thermography (b), and a microwave raster scan (c). Though methods (a) and (b) respond to boundaries, the outer contours look well contrasted in (a) and in some details different from (b) which provides more diffuse structures. The reason is that the thermal wave resolution differs from elastic wave resolution. The microwave image (c) does not only respond to boundary effects but also to the "optical path length", therefore it shows some additional information on structure behind the first boundary, e. g. the "finger-effect" related to thickness variations within the gas bubble. The outer contours are well defined as with ultrasonics, but again some details look different which may be due to interference

effects. So this is an example indicating that the appearance of a defect may depend on the method of inspection.

CHARACTERISATION OF FIBRE ORIENTATION

This is a field of relevance for many technical applications. The materials, however, may differ very much: Fibres may be glass or carbon, long (as in laminates) or short (for injection moulding). Correspondingly the demands on the technique of inspection may be different. Carbon fibres are electrical conductors. Consequently they are almost like metal for microwave inspection: Due to the strong reflection the depth range is confined to essentially one laminate layer. However, thermal conductivity makes them well suited for thermal wave inspection: Point heating results in a highly anisotropic thermal spreading [8-10]. If heat is deposited periodically one finds that the equal phase curves have elliptical shapes where ellipticity and its variation with distance from the center is significant: It allows to determine local fibre direction and, to some extent, also its dependence on the depth profile of orientation [9]. If a multi-point grid is projected on the sample under inspection to act as thermal wave sources in a lockin-thermography arrangement one may obtain this information in a very short time [11]. Ultrasonic backscattering [12] with a rotating transceiver arrangement (Fig. 3) allows for better angular resolution as shown in Fig. 4 where the position of the peaks indicate fibre directions which may depend on the time gate of the echo: The upper part of Fig. 4 was obtained with the early echo of the upper laminate layers, the lower correspondingly with the later echo of the lower layers of GFRP.

Figure 3. Ultrasonic backscattering. Reflection is strongest when fibre axis is perpendicular to ultrasonic beam, as shown for one fibre. The cone indicates only relative motion. In our experiments the sample is rotated.

a

b

Figure 4. Ultrasonic backscattering of GFRP: upper (a) and lower (b) part of laminate. Fibre directions differ by 90 degrees

GFRP has a very low electrical conductivity, hence it transmits microwaves which interact with the imbedded glass fibres due to the dielectric properties. This results in a dielectric anisotropy if there is fibre orientation. Therefore microwaves are suited for local orientation probing on a spot with some mm diameter. If such measurements are performed in a raster-like fashion one obtains an image of fibre orientation [13]. Compared to ultrasonic inspection this kind of imaging has the advantage of being a remote method. On the other hand it is not single-ended, both sides of the inspected sample must be accessible. Also the observed orientation is the average value taken across the local thickness. This disadvantage could recently be avoided by using resonance techniques providing depth sensitivity [14].

To analyse fibre orientation, microwaves and thermal waves are complementary methods. Their applicability depends on the conductivity of fibre material. Both methods compete with ultrasonic backscattering requiring physical contact with the sample. However, to measure angular distributions of fibres there is a disadvantage of using dielectric or thermal properties since they are described by a second rank tensor.

MONITORING OF PROCESSES

The mechanical properties of polymers depend strongly on the processes acting on them e. g. injection moulding, curing, diffusion, aging etc. One is interested to monitor these processes without affecting the component, so the question is which NDE method is sensitive to which process.

It is quite straight forward to monitor the processes via the mechanical properties which are affected. An example is the characterisation of curing with mechanical impedance spectroscopy where one observes how the real and imaginary part of modulus depend on frequency. Of course these changes are induced by molecular processes, so one can use as well dielectric spectroscopy. The results from both techniques are correlated [15], and it is not yet obvious which is more significant. In fact the combination of data from mechanical and dielectric measurements may be very efficient as shown in Fig. 1 where just one method would not provide any useful information. It should be mentioned that mechanical properties can be monitored without physical contact of the inspected sample. This can be done by excitation of resonances with modulated laser light and by detecting them with a laser vibrometer coupled to a lock-in-amplifier [16, 17].

CONCLUSION

We compared results obtained with different methods on the same kind of problems. In some cases the results are about the same though the interaction involved is quite different. In other cases there are differences which should allow to specify the result in more detail. If the result of a measurement is just a number, correlating plots may result in cluster formation allowing to distinguish between "good" and no "good" components. If the result is an image, correlation of methods is more demanding to use the full potential of information.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We like to express our thanks to AGEMA Infrared Systems for generous support of our research on lock-in-thermography. We are grateful to Mr. Aoki of DLR Stuttgart for kindly providing CFRP samples. J. Rantala is greatly indebted to Alexander von Humboldt-Foundation for financing his stay at University of Stuttgart. Part of the work has been funded as BMFT project 03N8006BO. Depth dependent fibre orientation is investigated in EC-project Nr. BRE2-CT92-0139. We are greatly indebted for the support of this Russian/German cooperation on behalf of the Federal Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Technology by the International Office of the Research Centre Karlsruhe.

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